

STUDENT ATHLETES AT RISK OF FAILING IN ACADEMICS: THE CASE OF PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In many rural Philippine schools, student-athletes are increasingly prioritizing sports over academic responsibilities, raising concerns among educators and parents alike. As young athletes strive to succeed both in the classroom and on the field, they often face difficulties in maintaining a healthy balance between academics and athletics. The purpose of this study is to explore the lived experiences and perspectives of student-athletes who place greater emphasis on sports, shedding light on the reasons, challenges, and coping mechanisms associated with this prioritization. Utilizing a qualitative case study approach, the research engaged seven male student-athletes from Grades 7 to 12, along with three teachers and four guardians. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and analyzed using thematic analysis to uncover common patterns across narratives. Five major themes emerged: passion for sports (interest in sports and sports efficacy) and incentives and rewards (travel opportunities, exemption from exams, and provision of materials) present the reasons; lack of balance between academics and sports (inability to focus on studies, lack of engagement in class, delayed submission of class requirements, and boredom) and physical exhaustion (burnout and tired from training) summarize the challenges; and social and academic support (support from peers and assistance of teachers) showed the coping mechanisms. The study concludes that while sports provide meaningful opportunities and motivation for student-athletes, a strong support system and structured academic interventions are essential to help them thrive holistically. It is recommended that schools implement flexible academic policies and mentorship programs to foster a more balanced and supportive environment for student-athletes.

Keywords: *Student-athletes, academic performance, sports prioritization, qualitative case study, rural education*

INTRODUCTION

Engaging students in sports promotes holistic development by fostering physical health, emotional resilience, and social well-being. Participation in athletics has been shown to support healthy weight management, enhance muscular strength, reduce anxiety, and build self-esteem (Eime et al., 2013; Donaldson & Ronan, 2006; Janssen & LeBlanc, 2010). These benefits make sports a vital component of student development. However, the demands of athletic involvement can sometimes conflict with academic responsibilities. Factors such as time constraints, socioeconomic challenges, and limited access to academic support may contribute to an imbalance, where sports begin to take precedence over education (Guest & Schneider, 2003; Miller et al., 2005).

In this context, it becomes crucial for schools, communities, and policymakers to establish supportive systems that enable student-athletes to succeed both academically and athletically. The Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes the importance of striking this balance. DepEd Order No. 36, s. 2016 outlines the criteria for granting awards to learners who excel in specific disciplines, including athletics. This policy underscores that recognition in sports must be complemented by satisfactory academic performance, thereby promoting a dual emphasis on excellence in both domains. Similarly, Republic Act No. 10676, known as the Student-Athletes Protection Act, along with its Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR), seeks to safeguard the amateur status of student-athletes while ensuring that their right to academic development is not compromised.

Despite these policy frameworks, ground-level data suggest growing concern. School-based reports from several divisions, including those in Region X, indicate an increasing number of student-athletes, particularly in junior high school, who are at risk of academic failure due to the prioritization of sports over studies (Division of Bukidnon Monitoring Reports, 2023). In Bukidnon, internal monitoring data from selected schools reveal that some student-athletes consistently underperform academically, especially during the sports season. While national statistics remain limited, these local trends highlight the need for a deeper investigation into the academic experiences of student-athletes.

This study seeks to examine this emerging issue by exploring the experiences of junior high school students in Bukidnon who are heavily involved in sports but show less commitment to their academic responsibilities. It aims to uncover their motivations, personal challenges, and the contextual factors influencing this behavior. By doing so, the research provides valuable insights into the dynamics that lead students to prioritize athletics over education.

Through qualitative analysis, this study investigates the environmental, institutional, and societal influences that contribute to the current state of academic underperformance among student-athletes. The goal is to critically assess these factors and propose

strategies for restoring academic focus while continuing to support athletic growth within the Philippine educational system.

Research Questions

Students in Bukidnon who put athletics and other sports activities ahead of their schoolwork are the focus of this research. This investigation will be guided by the following primary research questions:

1. What are the underlying reasons and motivations behind students' behavior, prioritizing sports activities above their academic responsibilities?
2. What are the challenges and difficulties experienced by the student-athletes?
3. What are the mechanisms done to address the challenges?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative case study design to deeply examine the lived experiences of student-athletes in a rural public secondary school in Quezon, Bukidnon. Rooted in the constructivist-interpretivist paradigm, the research aimed to understand the motivations, challenges, and systemic influences that lead student-athletes to prioritize sports particularly Sepak Takraw over academic pursuits. The rural setting was especially significant due to limited academic resources and the strong cultural emphasis on sports as a means of recognition and opportunity.

Participants included seven male Sepak Takraw student-athletes from Grades 7 to 12, three teachers, and four parents or guardians, all selected through purposive sampling. Inclusion criteria focused on active student-athletes not enrolled in the Special Program for Sports (SPS), while those primarily involved in academics or other extracurriculars were excluded. This participant group provided a range of perspectives across grade levels and athletic experiences.

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews conducted in Bisaya, with clarifications provided to ensure understanding. Interviews were audio-recorded and supported by field notes. To accommodate the participants' training schedules, interviews were conducted on rest days in comfortable environments. Ethical standards were strictly followed, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation.

Thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach, guided data interpretation. Transcripts were translated and manually coded, supplemented by web-based software to assist in organizing codes. Themes were refined with input from a

research mentor to ensure alignment with the study’s theoretical frameworks—Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and Social Learning Theory (SLT).

To ensure trustworthiness, the study applied member checking, maintained a detailed audit trail for dependability, and engaged in reflexive journaling to reduce bias. Transferability was supported by providing rich descriptions of the research context and participants. Ethical approval was granted by the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee, and all data handling complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

RESULTS

The data presented in this section are derived from interviews conducted by the researchers with seven male student-athletes, three teachers, and four parents or guardians from QUEMTRAS, Butong, Quezon, Bukidnon. Following each interview, the researchers systematically identified and coded the responses. The collected data were then categorized and documented. Through the application of a case study data analysis technique, three significant themes emerged from the analysis.

DISCUSSION

The following is a list of the themes and codes that came out of the interviews.

A. Reasons Behind Students' Behavior in Prioritizing Sports Activities Over Academic Responsibilities

The first theme reflects students' deep passion for sports, fueled by consistent training and the inspiration from successful athletes. Many developed this passion early, particularly in Sepak Takraw, and remain committed to their training despite challenges, demonstrating resilience and determination.

The second theme highlights the external motivators that encourage students to prioritize sports, such as travel opportunities, exam exemptions, special grades, and free gear like uniforms, shoes, and meals. These rewards, often provided by schools or local government, lessen academic burdens and reinforce their focus on athletics.

Theme 1: Passion For Sports

Category 1: Interest in Sports

The student-athletes' internal motivation to prioritize sports is evident in both parents' and teachers' observations. One parent highlighted their child's deep commitment to Sepak Takraw, noting self-initiated practice at home and a strong passion for the sport, stating, "Wala man sad. Makita man nako nga focus siya, nga happy siya sa iyang pagdula. Usahay gani magpractice siya sa balay, makit-an nimo ba na love niya ni nga sports. Belong ko ani, kaya gid nako, sa iyang kaugalingon, makaya jud niya maachieve jud niya" (Parent/Guardian Participant 1, Lines 41-44), meaning, "Not really. I can see that he's focused, that he's happy when playing. Sometimes he even practices at home; you can really tell he loves the sport. [He thinks] I belong here, I can do it, and he can really achieve it on his own." This reflects intrinsic motivation, which is crucial for long-term sports commitment (Almagro et al., 2020), and highlights how a strong athletic identity enhances dedication (Chun, 2023). The athlete's enthusiasm, self-driven practice, and belief in their ability align with Self-Determination Theory, emphasizing autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Alesi et al., 2019; Almagro et al., 2020). Teachers also observed the growing commitment of student-athletes, with one stating, "Napriority na pud nila ma'am ang sports bitaw. Nalove nila ang sports" (Teacher Participant 2, Line 31), meaning, "They prioritized the sports. They really came to love the sport." This shows how athletic identity leads athletes to focus on sports over other commitments, even when faced with challenges, as explained by Chun (2023). Alesi et al. (2019) also found that meaningful experiences and personal satisfaction further strengthen this attachment, guiding athletes' decisions and reinforcing their commitment.

Category Two: Sports Efficacy

This category explores factors influencing student-athletes' engagement with sports, including inspiration from successful athletes, early exposure to Sepak Takraw, and perseverance despite discouragement. Student-athletes expressed a desire to achieve similar success to varsity athletes, with one participant saying, "Gusto pud ko makaexperience sa ilang giagian ma'am na nakaabot silag Palarong Pambansa" (Student Participant 3, Lines 61–63), meaning, "I also want to experience what they achieved when they reached Palarong Pambansa." Teachers also observed that athletes were determined to maintain their positions, as one stated, "Naa man gud mi athletes sa Sepak Takraw na abot ug national, sa Palarong Pambansa. Murag ilaha pud siguro ikuan ang ilang dungog nga dili sila mawala" (Teacher Participant 2, Lines 29-30), meaning, "We have Sepak Takraw athletes who reached the national level, in Palarong Pambansa. They probably also want to preserve their honor, not to fade away." This intrinsic motivation aligns with Self-Determination Theory, which highlights the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in sustaining sports engagement (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Early involvement in Sepak Takraw also played a significant role, with several participants recalling how their passion for the sport began in elementary school. One student shared, "Kay sa una pa sa elementary, mao na na akong sports ma'am ba. Murag gusto ra gyud nako na nga sports kay wala naman koy lain nga sports na nabal-an" (Student Participant 5, Lines 28-30), meaning, "Because since elementary, this is my sport. I love this sport since I have never really known other sports." Additionally, perseverance despite discouragement was noted, as Student Participant 1 shared, "So, gidown ko oy. Naa man gud isa ka tao nga nag-ingon sa ako nga ayaw na pagtakraw oy kay di ka musikat ana. Mao to nakamotivate sa ako nga magepak takraw tong elementary ko" (Student Participant 1, Lines 80-81), meaning, "So, I felt down. There was this one person who told me, 'Don't play sepak takraw anymore, you won't become famous from that.' That's what actually motivated me, to play sepak takraw back when I was in elementary school." This reflects how athletic identity can transform negative feedback into motivation, as strong self-perception drives perseverance (Rintaugu et al., 2023; Edison et al., 2021).

Theme 2: Incentives and Rewards

Category 1: Travel Opportunities

This study identified travel opportunities as one of incentives student-athletes look forward to upon signing up to the sport activities. In the study, a student shared what they enjoy about joining the sport, stating that, "... makaadto kag lugar nga bisag asa, makadula ka ug kanang mga liga." (Student Participant 4, Lines 57-58). This can be translated to, "... you get to go to different places, and you can join various leagues (competitions)." This experience aligns to Pharaswal & Latif (2023) where sports engagement of the student improves their social development and motivation. Participating in extracurricular activities such as sports supports students' social development by fostering teamwork, communication, and a sense of belonging, while also

helping them build meaningful connections that boost motivation, long-term commitment, and overall enjoyment (Pharaswal & Latif, 2023).

In addition, Student participant 4 also discussed how he was encouraged to play when a teacher shared how far he can go, igniting own goals to compete on different and more competitive stages. In the interview, they disclosed, "Nagstart ko ani nga dula ma'am kay tungod ginakuan ko sa akong maestro sa una ma'am ba na muapil ko ani para taas kog maabot bitaw ma'am. Mao ning akong giapilan, kay basin diay makaabot kog Palaro. Pero wa pa ko kaabot ma'am, regional pa ko taman." (Student participant 4, Lines 68-71). This is translated to, "I started playing this sport because I was encouraged by my teacher before to join so I can reach higher. So, I joined, maybe I can actually reach Palaron. However, for now I still haven't gone there, I only reached the regionals." This goal-oriented behavior aligns with the Self-Determination Theory, particularly the concept of internalized extrinsic motivation, where students adopt valued goals—such as reaching higher levels of competition—based on encouragement from meaningful adults like teachers (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Parker et al., 2022). The teacher's support provided the social environment necessary for fostering competence and autonomy, leading to sustained sport participation.

Category 2: Exemption from Exams

This category explores how student-athletes often prioritize training over academics due to benefits such as exam exemptions, special points, and informal grading practices. One student shared, "Katong una-una, nakaexam ko pero karon exempted man mi ron" (Student Participant 1, Lines 125–126), which means, "Back then, I took the exam, but now we are exempted." The same student also explained that quiz scores were often based on the highest achiever among them: "Kung kinsa'y highest sa amoa, maoy among makuha kung naay mga quizzes" (Student Participant 1, Lines 94–95), meaning, "Whoever among us gets the highest score, that's what we will also get in the quizzes." These practices illustrate how academic expectations can be replaced by special treatment, encouraging students to favor athletic commitments over schoolwork (Thompson et al., 2022). Although such incentives might seem problematic, Sheehan et al. (2018) argue that when aligned with athletes' intrinsic goals, they can enhance mental well-being and performance. In many Philippine schools, this leniency continues due to informal systems that reward sports achievements with academic leniency. One teacher admitted, "Murag tagaan nalang namog chance na ing-ani ilang grado... Murag ana na time wala na sila magfocus sa academic, murag kana na time na palaro, sports ra sila focus" (Teacher Participant 2, Lines 77–81), meaning, "We give them a chance, especially if they brought honor to the school through competitions, so they focus only on sports during those times." While some athletes still earn good grades despite missing classes, these results may not always reflect actual academic performance. Instead, their grades often result from teacher support or adjustments, not learning outcomes. As one teacher mentioned, "Naa man pud uban nga dili sila maghatag pero naa silay mga ginahatag na special points... Kay luoy man gud ang bata nga gikapoy na padal-an pa ug module" (Teacher Participant 1, Lines 70–72), or "Some teachers don't assign modules but give special points because they feel bad for the tired students." This reflects how

teachers' empathy and institutional norms contribute to the informal accommodation of athletes. However, such practices may reinforce a strong athletic identity that can overshadow academic development (Yukhymenko–Lescroart, 2021). This identity-driven behavior presents a complex challenge for schools as they try to support both academic and athletic growth (Butlig et al., 2023; Thompson et al., 2024). As noted by Thompson et al. (2022), this prevailing culture in Philippine schools may inadvertently promote athletic achievement at the cost of academic integrity, raising concerns about educational equity and long-term learning outcomes.

Category 3: Provision of Materials

This category also tackle the provision of athlete uniform and meals as encouraging rewards for student athletes. While the interviews documented more insufficient fundings and support, the student participant showed appreciation to every materials they received usually in the form of varsity uniform including apparels and shoes as shared by Teacher Participant 2, stating that, “Apil ang LGU. Samot na tong nakaapil sa palarong pambansa, naay uniforms, makasponsor ug shoes.” (Teacher Participant 2, Lines 168-169). This translates to, “Including the LGU. Especially when they joined palarong Pambansa, they were sponsored with uniforms and shoes.” On the other hand, the meals prepared by teachers help replenish students' energy during training as as shared by Student Participant 6, “Kanang ginapatraining mi ma’am... ginatagaan pud mi ug snacks.” (Student Participant 6, Lines 138-139). This means, “They let us train and they also give us snacks.” These provisions not only promote physical readiness but also act as extrinsic motivators that sustain youth engagement in sports activities, especially in resource-constrained school settings (Pharaswal & Latif, 2023). Encouragement in the form of basic needs and symbolic recognition can significantly impact student morale, persistence, and overall participation in school-based athletic programs.

B. Challenges and Difficulties Experienced by the Student-Athletes

The first theme, Lack of Balance Between Academics and Sports, highlights how student-athletes struggle to focus on schoolwork due to training and games. They often feel disconnected in class, miss lessons, and prioritize sports over academics, leading to absences, late submissions, and low participation.

The second theme, Physical Exhaustion, shows how juggling school, home responsibilities, and intense training leads to burnout. Fatigue, physical strain, and lack of sleep reduce their energy and focus, making it hard to keep up with academic demands.

Theme 1: Lack Of Balance Between Academics and Sports

Category 1: Inability to focus on Studies

Student-athletes often struggle to focus on academics as their attention is frequently diverted by training and competition. One participant stated, “Usahay ma’am pag

magklase mi, dili kaayo ko gakuan, mas naa akong hunahuna sa takraw” (Student Participant 7, Lines 28–29), highlighting how their thoughts drift toward sports even during class. This internal conflict reflects the broader issue of role strain, where student-athletes must juggle the demands of both academic and athletic identities. Research by Yukhymenko–Lescroart (2021) and Yukhymenko–Lescroart & Sharma (2022) supports this, indicating that a strong identification with athletic roles can lead to lower academic performance. Moreover, sports-oriented school environments may unintentionally prioritize athletic excellence over academic engagement, further reinforcing this imbalance (Thompson et al., 2022).

Teachers also observe these patterns in the classroom. As Teacher Participant 3 explained, “Sa classroom gyud... murag bahin ilang hunahuna... usahay boringan na sila, usahay dili maminaw, matulog sa klase...” (Teacher Participant 3, Lines 29–35), describing how student-athletes often appear mentally absent, disinterested, or fatigued during lessons. These behaviors are consistent with findings by Santillan and Madrigal (2021), who noted that the combined pressures of school and sports create mental and emotional strain, leaving students distracted or anxious about missed lessons and future training. This continuous juggling of responsibilities contributes to fatigue, low motivation, and decreased participation in class. As emphasized by Thompson et al. (2023) and Alesi et al. (2019), such challenges underscore the need for structured support systems to help student-athletes manage their dual commitments effectively.

Category 2: Lack of Engagement in Class

This category highlights the declining classroom engagement among student-athletes, drawn from experiences categorized as “Disconnection to Unattended Lessons,” “More Interest in Training than Attending Class,” and “Anxiety to Participate in Class.” Many student-athletes feel disconnected during lessons due to frequent absences caused by training. As Student Participant 1 shared, they often feel left out, unable to understand discussions compared to just copying notes, stating, “Usahay di kaayo ko maka, lahi ra man gud sa magsulat ra ug sa magdiscussion” (Student Participant 1, Lines 100–104). This sense of being academically left behind is echoed in Hagiwara et al. (2022), who emphasized the emotional and cognitive struggles student-athletes face when their strong athletic identity disrupts academic participation. Teacher Participant 2 reinforced this by observing that students who are not physically present in class struggle to understand the lessons, saying, “dili sila kacope-up... wala man sila personally sa klase” (Lines 90–91). This difficulty is tied to the dual-role conflict outlined by Hart (2024), who noted that without structured support systems, student-athletes tend to disengage academically due to their inability to keep up with lessons and class activities.

The issue is further compounded when students prioritize sports over school. Student Participant 4 admitted shifting focus from academics to sports as the school year progressed, saying, “murag dili na kay magfocus na ko sa dula” (Lines 23–25), which aligns with Pellegrini and Hesla’s (2018) findings that increased athletic responsibilities often cause academic performance to decline. Teacher Participant 1 echoed this, noting students attend class irregularly unless it’s training time: “kung ting practice, perfect

attendance... kung ting klase, usahay na once a week lang musulod” (Lines 47–50). This behavior is consistent with Apaak and Yawson (2022) and Liu and Tareh (2024), who linked poor attendance and lack of academic discipline to widening learning gaps. Additionally, anxiety to participate in class due to academic unpreparedness also emerged. Student Participant 4 shared feeling nervous during oral activities because of missed lessons: “Kulbaan ko oy... Musulod dayon ko nga walay sulod akong utok” (Lines 78–94), a sentiment echoed by Teacher Participant 3 who said students fear being called on because they’re behind (Lines 37–38). Hart (2024), Edwards et al. (2023), and McCarthy (2019) collectively confirm that overcommitment to sports often results in classroom anxiety, reduced participation, and mental fatigue—highlighting the urgent need for academic support structures tailored to the unique demands of student-athletes.

Category 3: Delayed Submission of Class Requirements

This category addresses the frequent late submission of modules and class projects among student-athletes. As Student Participant 1 shared, “Usahay naa koy mga activities na mabehind oy. Kapuyan ko ba” (Lines 187–188), expressing how fatigue often causes delays in completing academic tasks. Pinto and Ramalheira (2017) support this by noting that while sports participation can enhance employability and soft skills, it also brings significant time and energy demands, which can interfere with academic responsibilities. They argue that student-athletes struggle to balance both domains without proper support or time management, leading to academic setbacks and physical exhaustion. This observation aligns with Teacher Participant 1, who stated, “Dili sila kacatch-up kay since nagtraining lagi sila... gakaalate ilang assignments” (Lines 19–20), confirming that training commitments contribute to late submissions.

Teacher Participant 1 further explained that some students only submit their work after being repeatedly reminded, stating, “Kung dili nimo ingnon nga, asa naman inyong modules, ipangpasa na, dili pud sila magpass” (Lines 81–86). This pattern of late or incomplete submissions is consistent with Apaak and Yawson’s (2022) findings, which highlight how athletic commitments often overshadow academic duties. Liu and Tareh (2024) also noted that many student-athletes lack academic discipline and need ongoing reminders to meet even basic requirements. This emphasizes the need for flexible academic structures and continuous teacher intervention to help student-athletes manage their dual commitments effectively.

Category 4: Boredom

A challenge faced by many student-athletes is their disinterest in class, often reflected as boredom. For example, Student Participant 7 shared, “...pero mas excited ko inig uli na kay excited ko magtakraw ba. Dili kaayo ko kafocus kay akong ginabantayan ang oras ba kung kanus-a ang ting-uli” (Lines 42-44), expressing how their focus is consumed by anticipating the end of class to engage in sports activities. This aligns with Apaak and Yawson (2022), who observed that student-athletes tend to lose classroom engagement due to emotional investment in sports, leading to reduced focus and retention during lessons. Similarly, Pharaswal and Latif (2023) noted that student motivation often

depends on the relevance of academic content to personal goals, such as sports aspirations, causing disengagement when students find academics less interesting.

Teacher Participant 3 also observed this disengagement, stating, "...Ang ilang hunahuna, layo, murag galupad-lupad ba nga unsay angay buhaton. Usahay boringan na sila, usahay dili maminaw, matulog sa klase..." (Lines 33–35), noting that student-athletes' minds often wander, causing boredom, lack of focus, or even sleepiness during class. Tsukahara et al. (2019) support this observation, finding that the demands of balancing athletics and academics often lead to cognitive overload and mental fatigue, which diminishes classroom attentiveness. These behaviors of distraction, boredom, and sleepiness reflect the struggle student-athletes face in maintaining focus while managing the pressures of both school and sport.

Theme 2: Physical Exhaustion

Category 1: Burnout

This category delves into the complex challenges that student-athletes face in managing responsibilities at school, home, and during training. Student Participant 1 shared the difficulties of balancing training with family obligations, stating, "Training? It's really just the training, it's very hard, very exhausting. Sometimes when I get home, there are family arguments. We almost had a serious fight—it's so tiring. I still have to think about training, and then there are things at home too." Parent/Gardian Participant 4 also observed the toll of training on their child, saying, "Sometimes when he comes home he looks very tired from the training, that I can't command him." These accounts highlight the significant stress student-athletes face when trying to manage both academic and athletic commitments, leading to physical exhaustion and emotional strain, which can extend to conflicts at home (Santos et al., 2020). The difficulty of balancing schoolwork and training is further confirmed by Teacher Participant 3, who noted, "One of the problems I really observed about them is the balancing their time between studying and training." This struggle is consistent with research by Apaak and Yawson (2022) and Liu and Taresh (2024), who emphasized that without structured guidance, the pressures of athletic schedules often overshadow academic duties, leading to academic gaps and diminished performance.

Moreover, physical exhaustion from training further complicates the balance, making it difficult for student-athletes to find the energy to study. Student Participant 7 explained, "Yes. Because it is very exhausting when we are training. Then, later at night we still have to answer the module, I cannot handle it." This experience aligns with Liu and Taresh (2024), who identified physical fatigue as a key barrier to academic productivity. Wang et al. (2024) also found that high-demand sports, such as badminton, often leave student-athletes physically drained, impairing their ability to engage in academic tasks. This physical exhaustion impacts their cognitive performance and sleep, hindering their ability to complete academic work effectively, thus exacerbating the challenges of managing both athletic and academic responsibilities.

Category 2: Tired from Training

The physical exhaustion student-athletes experience due to rigorous training schedules has significant effects on their academic performance. For example, Student Participant 1 described, “These days, we train for the whole day. At night, I write. But not always. Sometimes, there are times that I get too exhausted from the training.” Such physical fatigue is a common challenge among student-athletes, leading to reduced focus and academic burnout. Wang et al. (2024) observed that dual-career athletes often face sleep disruptions and heightened stress, making it difficult for them to manage academic tasks effectively. The prioritization of sports training, as noted by Teacher Participant 2, also contributes to the toll on students' physical capacity. This trend reflects the broader challenge of balancing the demands of both academic and athletic pursuits, as rigorous training can impair recovery and cognitive performance (Astridge et al., 2021).

Another factor exacerbating physical exhaustion is sleep deprivation. Teacher Participant 3 noted that some students “do not sleep enough” due to their training schedules, while Teacher Participant 1 observed that “Their body is exhausted from training, and then they get sleepy.” These observations align with research by Astridge et al. (2021) and Wang et al. (2024), which found that intense training combined with academic pressures often leads to insufficient sleep, undermining both physical and cognitive recovery. The lack of rest not only affects students' physical well-being but also their academic outcomes, suggesting that inadequate sleep due to excessive training and academic stress is a critical issue for student-athletes. These findings underscore the need for structured recovery periods and institutional support to help mitigate the negative effects of sleep deprivation and its impact on student-athletes' performance and overall well-being.

C. Mechanisms Addressing the Challenges Faced by Student-Athlete

One major theme emerged in the investigation about the mechanisms done to address the challenges faced by the student-athletes. The theme “Social and Academic Support” encompasses the essential roles of both peers and teachers in helping student-athletes balance their academic and athletic responsibilities.

Category 1: Support from Peers

Peers play a vital role in supporting student-athletes academically by helping them catch up with missed lessons and assignments. For instance, Student Participant 4 mentioned that they use group chats to ask classmates for help in catching up, while parents also encourage students to reach out to their peers about lessons missed during training. This peer support is crucial for student-athletes, as research shows that academic success is more likely when they receive assistance from their peers. Studies by Fortuna et al. (2022) and Gehreke et al. (2024) support the positive impact of peer mentoring, which helps student-athletes adjust to the dual demands of academics and athletics, ensuring that they can stay engaged in both areas. Additionally, peers not only inform others about missed lessons but also help them complete projects, creating an environment of mutual support that promotes academic success. Cho et al. (2020) emphasize that peer support

is directly linked to better emotional well-being and motivation, which enhances students' academic engagement.

Theme 1: Social and Academic Support

Category 2: Assistance of Teachers

Teachers provide essential support to student-athletes by using modules, online materials, and flexible assessments to help them catch up on missed lessons. For example, Teacher Participant 3 described using recorded lessons and online materials so students can study during their downtime. This approach supports self-directed learning, a strategy identified by Roberson et al. (2021) as beneficial for students with limited time due to their athletic commitments. Some teachers also use special projects as supplementary assignments, ensuring that athletes can still meet academic requirements. Abdullah et al. (2023) note that such alternative assessments help students demonstrate understanding, even when traditional class participation is not possible. Additionally, teachers also ensure that student-athletes are well-fed by organizing meal contributions and snacks, reinforcing the importance of support beyond academics. Teacher Participant 3 explained how their team provides meals and snacks for athletes during training, which aligns with findings by Abdullah et al. (2023) and Roberson et al. (2021), who emphasize that such initiatives boost motivation and well-being, ensuring that student-athletes are supported both physically and academically.

Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to explore the lived experiences of students-athletes in Bukidnon, specifically the underlying reasons and motivations why students prioritize sports activities over their academic responsibilities, the challenges and difficulties they experience, and the mechanisms done to address the problems associated with their studies. Through qualitative interviews and thematic analysis, the study aimed to uncover personal, social, and institutional factors that lead to this behavior. Based on the depth of participant responses and the clarity of emerging themes, the study successfully achieved its purpose by presenting a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of student-athletes who place athletics above academics.

The findings revealed five themes: Passion for sports and incentives and rewards present the students' reasons for prioritizing sports above academics; lack of balance between academics and sports and physical exhaustion summarizes the challenges and difficulties faced by the students; and social and academic support represent the mechanisms supporting the student athletes with their unique needs and struggles. These themes demonstrate that while passion and incentives drive students to pursue sports, issues like classroom fatigue, academic disengagement, and institutional leniency reinforce this imbalance. Students often identify more strongly as athletes than learners, which can lead to a gradual decline in academic engagement and performance.

Anchoring these findings within Self-Determination Theory and Social Learning Theory provided a theoretical lens through which to understand students' behavior. The satisfaction of psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness explains their deep involvement in sports. Meanwhile, the reinforcement of athletic identity by teachers, coaches, peers, and family members aligns with Social Learning Theory's emphasis on modeling and social influence. These theories explain why students internalize sports as their primary identity, often at the expense of academic development. What comes next is a call for educational stakeholders to recognize and respond to this growing imbalance. Schools must reframe their systems to prioritize academic success alongside athletic achievement equally. This includes reevaluating support structures, curriculum design, and the implementation of targeted programs such as time management education and differentiated academic support for student-athletes. Institutions can foster environments where students no longer have to choose between excelling in sports or academics, but are instead empowered to thrive in both.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed to address the challenges uncovered in the study and to promote a more balanced approach to academic and athletic development among student-athletes in Bukidnon.

1. The Special Program for Sports (SPS) may be institutionalized by school administrators to provide structured support that helps student-athletes balance their athletic training with academic responsibilities, addressing the challenge of students identifying more as athletes than learners.
2. School heads and district supervisors may initiate and facilitate regular capacity-building programs to train and empower teachers in effectively addressing the unique academic needs of student-athletes.
3. MAPEH teachers may integrate structured time management modules into Physical Education classes as part of life skills education to help student-athletes cope with overlapping academic and sports commitments.
4. Academic coordinators and subject teachers may collaboratively review and refine grading policies to ensure fairness and academic integrity, while still offering reasonable accommodations for student-athletes.
5. Guidance counselors may develop and implement holistic wellness programs that recognize and respond to the physical fatigue and mental stress experienced by student-athletes, incorporating strategies such as rest, recovery, academic consultation, and emotional support.
6. Homeroom advisers may organize regular parent orientation and feedback sessions specifically designed for parents of student-athletes to strengthen parental involvement and collaboratively develop academic monitoring strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical framework of this qualitative study ensured the protection and well-being of participants while maintaining the integrity of the research. Informed consent was obtained from both parents and students, respecting the Belmont Principle of Respect for Persons. Participants were thoroughly informed about the study's purpose and procedures, and their participation was voluntary, with the option to withdraw without consequence. The study received approval from the Research Ethics Committee, ensuring compliance with ethical standards and institutional protocols. Confidentiality was prioritized, with personal data anonymized and securely stored, in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Throughout the research, the researcher upheld principles of transparency, honesty, and respect for participants. Data collection and analysis were guided by strict ethical considerations, ensuring no harm to participants' privacy or dignity. The researcher also practiced reflexivity, examining personal biases to maintain objectivity. To ensure trustworthiness, member checking was employed, allowing participants to validate the findings, while feedback from colleagues and experts was incorporated to strengthen the study's rigor and credibility.

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